

Enhancing Parental Collaboration in Classroom Activities: Stories of Grade Three Teachers

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Abstract. This study explores and investigates the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and lessons learned from the experiences of grade three teachers in enhancing parental collaborations in rural areas. A qualitative approach to research from the 8 Grade three teachers from Mati South District, Division of Mati City, on the lived experiences of grade three teachers in enhancing parental collaborations in rural areas were observed: collaborating with the community, challenging, trust and respect, and dedication and optimism. Teachers coping mechanisms for enhancing parental collaborations in rural areas were as follows: boosting cooperation, keeping the line of communication open, and capacitating teachers. Through their experiences and coping mechanisms, we generated new knowledge and ideas on the challenges the grade three teachers encountered in enhancing parental collaborations in rural areas. Finally, the lessons learned from the experiences of grade three teachers in enhancing parental collaborations in rural areas were attendance to training and seminars, effective communication, and strengthened collaboration. These themes could be described as input in the successful crafting and conduct of training for grade three teachers to capacitate them on the different strategies and techniques in ensuring the enhancement of parental collaborations in rural areas.

KEY WORDS

1. Teachers' lived experiences
2. coping mechanisms
3. lessons learned
4. parental collaborations

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1. Introduction

Considering all aspects of a child's personality can make their development possible. Life Skill Education plays an integral part in everyone's life. In life skill education, a child's overall personality is considered. It gives strength to handle any situation and courage to face the struggle to achieve any target. By adding life skill education to the school curriculum, better results can be achieved. Emerging as early as the 1880s, home economics aimed not only to teach women how to cook and sew but also to provide an avenue for young women to attend college. Home economics was not until the early 1900s that it became an organized area of study, developed by Catherine Beecher and Ellen Swallow Richards, who founded the American Association of Family and Consumer Sciences. These pioneering women first set out the seven areas of home economics to teach girls how to care for a home and family properly and to open new career avenues. Now known as family and consumer science, according to the Los Angeles Times, modern home economics courses now offer a more inclusive education

to all students, including those in high school. (Hammond, 2021). TLE is geared toward the development of technological proficiency and is anchored on knowledge and information, entrepreneurial concepts, process and delivery, work values, and life skills. Livelihood education that works is built on adequate mastery of knowledge and information, skills and processes, and the acquisition of the right work values and life skills. The functional TLE equips students with skills for lifelong learning. TLE is concerned only with the mere definition of terms, which is meaningless and shallow. Therefore, teaching TLE means teaching facts, concepts, skills, and values (Hammond, 2021). The students should know that in all occupational endeavors, they should know about marketing and selling their goods or services, and consequently, bookkeeping and accounting. Moreover, entrepreneurship or self-employment students need this knowledge when running their businesses. The schools should take measures to provide adequate and needed essential facilities, tools, equipment, supplies, and materials to fully implement their program of practical arts in order to attract more students in the interest of improved learning. The institutions need to exert more outstanding efforts in securing more community resources to aid in implementing the program and to argue insufficient funding to purchase materials to enrich curricular offerings. Teachers must improve their skills and competence in imparting knowledge to their students. Likewise, the institutions should adequately provide for the shortage, such as lack of books, instructional materials, equipment/tools, and the like, in order that the students may be able to derive the instruction. (Tan, 2021). Bagood (2020) also added that identified teaching personnel, together with the Education Program Supervisors, prepared modules starting in May 2020 in all subjects for all grade/year levels across four quarters per the "Most Essential Learning Competencies." These self-learning modules are al-

ready considered learning packages containing pre-tests, discussions, and a series of evaluations/assessments. They are distributed to all learners with the modular learning class schedule. Indeed, this kind of instructional modality has been followed by public school teachers all over the Philippines. Teachers play a vital role in continuously delivering quality education amid the pandemic. Despite the threats of the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers continue to serve by formulating modules as the learning guide for students. The teacher thus becomes a facilitator in the development of the student, both as a member of their community and a member of their society. However, Malipot (2020) stressed that teachers also air their problems on modular distance learning. Bagood (2020) highlighted that as front liners in the educational system, they had undergone various training and seminars to be more equipped to deliver better education amid the COVID-19 pandemic, as it is a norm of the department to train teachers not just for professional growth but to become ready for unexpected circumstances, especially in the teaching of Technology and Livelihood Education. With all of these changes, teachers are forced to adapt and upskill to monitor the status of the learners continually. Information technology skills become a significant part of learning during the new normal to facilitate instruction better, give feedback, and reach struggling learners remotely. This has also changed the dynamics of skill acquisition for life skills being cascaded to elementary learners. To ease the skepticism of some teachers, learners and parents, this study is pursued to find solutions to the critical issues and concerns regarding the Utilization of Self Learning Module in Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education Specializations through highlighting actions for Learner Support. The researcher is optimistic that this intervention could backup TLE students and teachers in the teaching-learning process, encourage open communications and

inspires students in their self-learning journey. Likewise, it maybe a great help in raising awareness among all subject teachers, learners, school head and the general populace in reaching more action to Modular Teaching- Learning, especially in the field of TLE and its Specialization courses. To ease the skepticism of some teachers, learners, and parents, this study was pursued to find solutions to the critical issues and concerns regarding the Utilization of the Self Learning Modules in Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education Specializations by

highlighting actions for Learner Support. The researcher was optimistic that the results of this study could back up TLE students and teachers in the teaching-learning process, encourage open communication, and inspire students in their self-learning journey. Likewise, it may be a great help in raising awareness among all subject teachers, learners, school heads, and the general populace in reaching more action to Modular Teaching-Learning, especially in TLE and its Specialization courses.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study aimed to explore the realities of the pedagogical experiences of elementary teachers in teaching Technology and Livelihood Education beyond the global pandemic. This study may be beneficial for administrators, as the data gathered served as research-based information that will be useful in motivating and giving technical assistance to teachers in innovating the methodologies applied in the context of the school in teaching TLE, including its challenges and opportunities. This study may also be beneficial for teachers in improving the teaching-learning process in the distance learning setup, thereby improving academic proficiency. Further, the results of this research provided comprehensive data for conducting future research with similar or relevant scope.

- 1.2. Research Questions*—The primary research questions of this study are the following:
- (1) What are Elementary teachers' perceptions in teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in acquiring 21st-century skills?
 - (2) What are the challenges encountered by the teachers in teaching TLE?
 - (3) What educational management insights are gained by the teachers in teaching TLE in blended learning?

1.3. Significant of the Study—This study may be significant to the following: DepEd Officials. The finding of this study served as an empirical basis for education officials to develop new programs related to ICT integration in the classroom. Allocating more funds for technological innovation is also a good outcome of the study. School Administrators. The data gathered served as research-based information useful in motivating and providing technical assistance to teachers in innovating the methodologies applied in the school context in information communication technology, including its challenges and opportunities. Teachers. The study's findings served as the basis for improving the teaching-learning process in the distance learn-

ing setup, thereby improving academic proficiency with the use of technological innovations. This research heard the voices of the teachers in the field with whatever concerns they have about integrating ICT in the classroom. Stakeholders. The community was the best recipient of integrating ICT in the classroom. The data gathered from this research provided a good basis for stakeholders to help improve the school's technological resources. Future Researchers. The results generated from this research provided comprehensive data for conducting future research with similar or relevant scope. This is an additional empirical data and update on the status of ICT integration in schools, especially beyond the era of the global health crisis.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The knowledge acquisition of TLE teachers in 21st-century education can be anchored in the Constructivist Learning Theory. Constructivism is based on the work of Jean Piaget, Jerome Bruner, Ernst von Glaserfeld, and Lev Vygotsky. It is a learner-centered approach that suggests that students actively "construct" their knowledge. Each individual's reality is determined by prior knowledge, beliefs, and experiences. Because learning is based on personal experiences, each student's learning is unique. In other words, "Constructivist approaches emphasize learners actively constructing their knowledge rather than passively receiving information transmitted to them from teachers and textbooks. From a constructivist perspective, knowledge cannot simply be given to students: Students must construct their meanings" (Stage, Muller, Kinzie and Simmons, 1998, p. 35). Constructivist learning theory is based upon numerous principles, such as students learn by doing. When students have agency in their learning, they build their capacity as learners and improve their abilities, skills, and expertise. Additionally, constructivists believe that learning is a social activity and is best accomplished when students are engaged in activities involving their peers, families, and communities to solve problems and accomplish learning tasks. Learning is contextual, and teachers must design learning activities considering students' prior knowledge, beliefs, and experiences. Finally, constructivists believe that students' intrinsic motivation is the key to effective learning and student engagement. Students will not learn appropriately if they are not motivated to do so (Hinton, 2021). The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there were two interconnected variables. These variables were the perceptions of Elementary teachers in teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in acquiring 21st-century skills, Challenges encountered by the teachers in teaching TLE, and educational management insights gained by the teachers teaching TLE in the blended learning modality.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. As elaborated in this chapter, exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It established the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. *Ontology*. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of TLE teachers in teaching the TLE subject were investigated. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different per-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

spectives. The answers of the participants in the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. The responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This is the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), stated that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants. He suggested that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. This study intended to gather information from the experiences of TLE teachers in teaching the TLE subject. It was assured that close interaction was established with the participants to gain

direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. This was the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) stated that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discussed values that shape the narrative and included his or her interpretation in conjunction with the participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher wrote in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, using qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to understand the challenges of TLE teachers in teaching the TLE subject.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology is different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). This study explored the lived experiences of TLE teachers in teaching the subject, particularly those teachers from Manuel M. Garcia Elementary School, Division of Davao Oriental. The researcher dived in knowing the deeper meaning of their experiences became the basis for doing qualitative research, which is considered helpful in looking for meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers so that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological re-

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design since it focused on the realities of TLE teachers in teaching the subject. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also

search was based on two premises. The first was that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research is that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

added that phenomenology, with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempted to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily used in qualitative research. They occurred when researchers asked one or more participants general, open-ended questions and recorded their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to fur-

ther investigate their responses. In this qualitative research, interviews were used to explore the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in conducting interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees would say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on Quad's (2016) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the expe-

riences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher needed to decide how and when his or her observations would be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the TLE teachers' experiences and feelings towards teaching the subject, the researcher intended to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were the 7 elementary TLE teachers of Congressman Manuel M. Garcia Elem. School, Division of Davao Oriental. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least 5 years; (2) must employ blended modality in teaching TLE during the pandemic; (3) must

be elementary teachers handling TLE. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical con-

siderations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needed to adhere to the research aims, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and error prevention. Social Value. Research is essential to the society.

In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among the TLE teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the interest of the researcher is the challenges faced by the TLE teachers in teaching the subject. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009) adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as a researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks,

Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher has ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so that there were no conflicts of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way, was avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication-related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Trans-

parency. The results of the study were accessed by the participants and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and was placed on CD or other storage devices which can be requested from the researcher to provide. In addition, by learning from the results of the study, TLE teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview is carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher was qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-

adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to ensure that the study could be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher is responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher took up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducted interviews with the participants and guided them in the process. The researcher interpreted ideas and responded based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge,

thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implemented the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assessed himself and sought help from the research adviser and other professionals. These helped him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and em-

ploying Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensured different ways of making a record of what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were secured adequately as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding were clearly articulated to participants and were approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity amidst the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015, or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings in implementing non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools.

began. Analyst of data. The researcher saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensured that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organized and presented the data, as well as the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The findings of the study were presented, too, by the research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were then categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered

was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the partic-

ipants in order to come up with patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding is also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a data reduction method; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the

data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes is a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing-up involved weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. The researcher made sure of the experiences of TLE teachers in teaching the subject.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher became familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation or field notes) and gained an

overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher became immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher became aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and noted them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection depends on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations). Identifying a thematic framework, the second stage, occurred

after familiarization when the researcher recognized emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes issues; however, it is at this stage that the researcher allowed the data to dictate the themes and issues. To achieve this end, the researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means that one identifies portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (i.e., transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and

annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis was able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: "defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies" (Ritchie Spencer, 1994, p. 186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations were reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echoed the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substituted data trustworthiness, which consists of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility involved establishing that the findings of the research were credible or believable from the perspective of the participant. Observing the attributes of prolonged engagement is where credibility contributed to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the issue of credibility, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of satura-

tion. Meanwhile, transferability was the degree to which the findings were generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job of describing the research context and assumptions that were relevant. On the other hand, dependability was the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher made sure that the study's findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability is the degree to which findings could be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also made sure that the findings were free from bias.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with the research questions and requirements of this study. The participants disclosed their experiences of grade three teachers in enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas. The grade three teachers' experiences were also discussed as to how they perform their functions in their respective schools.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

3.1. Experiences of Grade Three Teachers' in Enhancing Parental Collaboration—Collaboration between parents and teachers is a powerful tool in the classroom. According to Lazar and Slostad's article (1999). "Parent-teacher partnerships bring a community of adults together to work toward a common goal of helping students succeed. Students deserve support, and therefore, the collaboration between parents and teachers is instrumental to enhancing students' success in the classroom. By having this collaboration between teachers and parents, students can have a positive impact in the social context as well as academics. This collaboration can set a clear path of continued success at all grade levels, which will, in turn, positively affect the student's career. Research indicates that when parents and teachers work together, students benefit both socially and academically. (Lazar Slostad, 1999). Creating a partnership between parents and teachers requires time to build relationships and establish trust, which allows parents to be well-informed and enable appropriate decisions that affect their child's learning experience at school and at home. A strong school-home partnership builds a positive attitude towards school and learning in children.

3.1.1. Collaborating with the community—Collaborating with the community pertains to identifying and integrating community services and resources to support and strengthen schools, students, and their families. It also includes information for students and families on community health, cultural, recreational, and social support, and other program services, information on community activities that link to learning skills and talents, and summer programs for students. Each of these factors can lead to various results for students, parents, teaching practices, and the school climate. In addition, each includes many different practices of partnership and lastly, these pose challenges to involve all families. Durisik Masa (2017) Epstein (2001; 2009) agrees with Durisik and considers it to be significant for each school. It is for the school to choose what factors are believed to be most likely to assist the school in reaching its goals for academic success and to develop a climate of alliance between homes and the school. Even though the primary focus of these six factors is to promote academic achievements, they also contribute to various results for both parents and teachers (Epstein, 2003, 2009). For instance, it may be presumed that parents will gain more self-confidence in their role as parents, will show leadership with decision-making and will have more effective and productive communication with their children with regard to school work, and will have more communication with other parents at the school. According to Henderson and Berla (2004), parents who are involved with their education also develop a more positive attitude towards the school and its staff and gain more confidence in assisting their children with homework. In addition, they are more likely to gather support for the school and its program in the community and become more active community members. For teachers, the benefits may be presumed to be better communication with parents, a deeper understanding of the families of their students and their situation, and more effective communication with both the homes and the community.

3.1.2. Challenging—The relationship that exists between parents and teachers can be described as both rewarding and challenging (Lasky, 2000). Research has documented the critical role that parental involvement plays in children's learning. Yet, establishing appropriate relationships with parents can be challenging for schools and personnel. Lightfoot (1978) labeled parents and teachers as "worlds apart" because they had different, often con-

fluctuating feelings and responsibilities for children. Ogawa (1996) noted that schools “bridge and buffer” themselves from “uncertainties that parents might introduce”. Epstein (1990) described interactive relationships between home, school, and community as having “overlapping spheres of influence” on children. Other researchers have identified challenges in establishing collaborative home–school relationships; among them are parents’ balancing work lives and school involvement (Smrekar, 1996), teachers’ sharing power with parents (Lawson Briar-Lawson, 1997), and schools’ overcoming bureaucratic structures that hinder collaboration (Henry, 1996). Furthermore, Munn (1985, 1993), Toomey (1996), and Moore and Lasky (1999) recognized that some government initiatives could hamper the partnership between parents and teachers, the reasons being that parents could be more interfering, thereby pressuring teachers to retreat from their partnership. In addition, barriers have been noted from both the parents’ and teachers’ perspectives and professional boundaries erected by teachers (Crozier, 1999). Any misunderstandings can limit parental involvement in a school.

3.1.3. Trust and Respect—Trust and respect between parents and teachers are critical in successful school-family cooperation. Trust was seen as a personality attribute that includes optimism, a belief in collaboration, and confidence that individuals can resolve their differences and live a satisfactory social life together (Newton, 2004). Mutual respect occurs when people value each other’s skills, knowledge, and competence (Adams Christenson, 2000; Fewster-Thuente, 2015; Hallam et al., 2015). Mutual respect is developed when ideas and knowledge are valued; there is confidence in each other’s abilities and flexibility to resolve conflict constructively (Tucker Schwartz, 2013). One of the most important factors in facilitating parent-teacher partnerships and par-

Implementing the Goals 2000: Educate America Act in the US has reintroduced parents into the schools, stressing the importance of parent-school collaborations and partnerships. While this may be viewed as strengthening the educational system, it has minimal impact if school personnel are not trained to partner with families. Historically, teacher education programs nationwide have done little to prepare pre-service teachers to work with families, and this trend continues today (LeRoux, 2001; Rothstein-Fisch, 1997; Shartrand et al., 1994). Studies have also shown that some teachers may lack the communication skills and competencies to build effective partnerships with parents (Gartmeier et al., 2016). Also, there are sometimes discrepancies between teacher and parental expectations regarding curriculum-centered pedagogies versus student-centered approaches to teaching and learning (Torff, 2015), resulting in a lack of understanding between teachers and parents about student learning processes and teachers’ instructional processes. To help to mitigate these discrepancies, teachers need to have the appropriate competencies for developing positive relationships with parents.

ents’ involvement in their children’s education is mutual trust between teachers and parents (Clarke et al., 2000; Tschannen-Moran, 2001). When working together as partners, parents and teachers communicate more effectively, develop stronger relationships, like trust and respect, and develop skills to support children’s behaviors and learning. Trust and open communication are necessary for understanding another individual’s level of competence, skills, and knowledge, and mutual respect is often considered in association with trust and open communication (Pullon, 2008). Teachers have to inform parents and establish a relationship of mutual trust with the parents. Adams and Christenson (2000) define trust in the parent-teacher relationship as “confidence that another person will act to bene-

fit or sustain the relationship, or the implicit or explicit goals of the relationship, to achieve positive student outcomes”. Previous research has shown that parent-teacher relationships have the most beneficial outcomes when they represent a true partnership, including two-way communication, mutual respect, and trust between parents and the teacher, as well as shared values and expectations concerning how to support the child (e.g., Adams Christenson, 2000; Clarke et al., 2000; Galindo Sheldon, 2012) The seven types of parental involvement, which are parenting, learning at home, connecting, communicat-

ing, volunteering, decision-making, and community collaboration, have a positive relationship with teachers’ trust in parents and students. (Chu, 2007). Additionally, when parents participate in their children’s education, both at home and at school, and experience relationships with teachers characterized by mutuality, warmth, and respect, students have higher achievement, demonstrate increased achievement motivation, and show higher levels of emotional, social, and behavioral adjustment (e.g., Fan Chen, 2001; Kim et al., 2013; Powell et al., 2010).

3.1.4. Dedication and Optimism—Dedication and optimism are much-needed traits in a school setting, where a teacher deals with varied kinds of people. Academically optimistic schools contain teachers who believe they “can make a difference, that students can learn, and that academic performance can be achieved” (Hoy et al., 2006). Some of the most effective teachers appear to be those teachers who seem to remain confident in their ability to make a difference with all students despite the numerous obstacles that can impact the learning process. A teacher’s positive belief that he or she can make a difference in the academic performance of students by emphasizing academics and learning, by trusting parents and students to cooperate in the process, and by believing in his or her own capacity to overcome difficulties and react to failure with resilience and perseverance (Woolfolk Hoy et al., 2008) can impact a student’s academic success is a sign of dedication and optimism In some schools in the UK, posts of special responsibility are dedicated to parental involvement. Extensive programs of meetings with parents are arranged, some to explain the curriculum and schools’ practice, some to report progress, some to consider individual pupils, and some to celebrate success. Some schools provide courses for par-

ents on curriculum-relevant topics; others take special measures such as arranging transport to school to meet particular parents’ needs. Above all, good schools in this respect are, on the one hand, dedicated to constructive listening and, on the other, to the forthright pursuit of increased educational standards. One remarkable program that moved a school from near closure to prize-winning status in a few years is the “INSTEP” project, which was a program dedicated to enhancing home-school links. On the part of the school, there was a determination to make a step-wise change here and, more broadly, in-home/school links. A special team was installed. Cast as a resource to the whole school, it was dedicated to working with parents. The team mediated at many levels between parents, the school’s teaching and learning activities, and, more importantly, between parents and teachers. Positive parent-school communications benefit parents. The manner in which schools communicate and interact with parents affects the extent and quality of parents’ home involvement with their children’s learning. Because of the teacher’s constant dedication to parent-teacher collaboration, parents benefit from being involved in their children’s education by getting ideas from the school on how to help and support their children and by

Fig. 3. The Emerging Themes on the Experiences of the Grade Three Teachers in Enhancing Parental Collaboration in Rural Area

learning more about the school’s academic program and how it works. Perhaps most importantly, parents benefit by becoming more confident about the value of their school involvement. Parents develop a greater appreciation for their important role in their children’s education. At the same time, research shows that parental involvement can free teachers to focus more on teaching children. Also, by having more contact with parents, teachers learn more about students’ needs and home environment, which is information they can apply toward bet-

ter meeting those needs. Parents involved tend to have a more positive view of teachers, which results in improved teacher morale. Here are some of the testimonies of the study participants. Here are some of the testimonies of the study participants.

Figure 3 shows the experiences of grade three teachers in enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas and the emergence of the three themes: collaborating with the community, challenging experiences, Trust and Respect, dedication, and optimism.

3.2. *Mechanisms Used by Grade Three Teachers*—It is found that there is poor involvement of parents from high-poverty communities,

which happen to be mostly rural (Matshe, 2014; Mncube, 2010; Msila, 2012), partnerships with parents appear to be a strength for rural schools

in various other international contexts (Byun et al., 2012; Ma et al., 2014; Manzo, 2016; Robinson Volpe, 2015; Semke Sheridan, 2012; Stelmach, 2011). In the USA, a comprehensive review of studies by Semke and Sheridan (2012) shows that parental involvement is a strength for high-poverty high-performing schools. Along the same lines, a study conducted in the USA in 73 schools across 34 states by Byun et al. (2012) found that rural parents are interested in the education of their children, and they were involved, even though this was mostly among two-parent families. Manzo (2016) conducted a mixed methods study with rural Latino parents in California on their involvement in kinder-

garten schools and the findings suggest the opposite of the dominant discourse about rural parents. In this study, it surfaced that rural Latino parents partnered with teachers in encouraging children to attend school and helping other parents when they encounter problems (Manzo, 2016). These findings correspond with another study of Latino rural parents of low socioeconomic status, conducted by Ceballo, Maurizi, Suarez, and Aretakis (2014), and with another study conducted by Robinson and Volpe (2015) among 16 parents with high poverty status from two rural elementary schools in Appalachian district.

3.2.1. Boosting Collaboration—In enhancing relationships, Gordon and Louis (2009) suggest that principals and teachers need to create a culture of shared leadership and responsibility to enhance parents' involvement. On how the relationship between schools and parents can be enhanced, there is a suggestion that school leaders and policymakers should provide culturally and linguistically appropriate programs for parents and that policies should cater for different parental conditions and address inequalities that arise during school-parents interactions (Brien Stelmach, 2009; Manzo, 2016). Besides

policies, technology has also been linked to enhancing parental involvement (Lewin Luckin, 2010). The bigger question would be, how will technology be utilized with parents with backgrounds characterized by education and poverty deprivation? On this, Lewin and Luckin (2010) further suggest that focused support to parents in the use of technology is required and school leaders, we suggest, should see to it that this kind of support is provided. Further, on the role of schools, Goshin and Mertsalova (2018, p. 70) use Epstein's (2001) typology of involvement to provide a detailed account of how school leaders can strengthen relationships with parents.

3.2.2. Keeping the Line of Communication Open—Parent-teacher communication begins at the start of a school year and lasts until students progress to the next grade. Teachers and parents will make introductions and gradually establish a relationship based on what they have in common: the student. Parent-teacher communication can take place in person, typically through parent-teacher conferences or during student drop-off or pick-up times. Teachers can also reach out to parents on the phone or by

email (Zieger et al., J. 2012). Through open communication with parents, teachers can share information about a student's good work and achievements. If a student begins to struggle with a certain subject or exhibits behavioral problems, the parent will already have a relationship with the teacher, which helps facilitate parent-teacher collaboration. This cooperative relationship empowers parents to step in and support the student at home, supplementing what the teacher is doing at school (Virginia

Department of Education, 2002). According to Graham-Clay (2005) when parents communicate with teachers to discover their children's needs, students see that their family is looking out for them and wants them to be successful. Parents who assist children with homework and

remind them to study for tests can increase their chances of short-term and long-term success by helping them develop important habits. Parents can also support children and help boost their confidence by encouraging them when they do well in school.

3.2.3. *Capacitating Teachers*—A teacher-family partnership is a relationship in which families and professionals collaborate, capitalizing on each other's judgments and expertise to increase the benefits of education for students, families, and professionals (Turnbull et al., 2010; Bayat, 2012). The establishment of partnerships is not to be by chance or without structure. The school leadership should be committed to and encourage school family partnerships through shared responsibilities, shared decision-making, and parity for all participants (Smith et al., 2012). For students with disabilities in inclusion settings, the integration of professional efforts and involvement of parents are required. There is a need for administrators, teachers, aides, volunteers, and members of the interdisciplinary team to work together. In addition to benefiting the children, professional growth takes place as professionals collaboratively search for ways to provide for children with disabilities in an inclusive setting. During the search process, it will necessitate ways to develop a partnership with parents. To make the partnership a success, it is essential to listen to parents' concerns, consult with them on a continuous basis, and make use of the knowledge that they possess about their children (Allen Cowdery, 2009). There are two major functions of parental involvement. It provides an ongoing reinforcement system that supports the efforts of the program while it is underway and it tends to maintain and accentuate the child's gains after the program ends (Allen Cowdery, 2009). To help ensure that partnerships operate effectively,

Turnbull et al. (2010) developed seven principles of partnerships. Communication, professional competence, respect, commitment, equality, advocacy, and trust are principles. The participants' narratives above can be generalized to describe how they work together and use technology to aid in teaching and other administrative functions. This helps them feel like they are part of the school community and encourages them to be more involved in their child's education. We also hold parent-teacher conferences regularly to discuss their child's progress and identify areas for improvement. Some qualities of a good teacher include communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability, empathy, and patience skills. Other characteristics of effective teaching include an engaging classroom presence, value in real-world learning, exchange of best practices, and a lifelong love of learning. Teachers play a vital role in improving the quality of the teaching and learning process. Good teachers are very important to raise student achievement; hence, enhancing teachers' quality is of prime importance in the many educational reform efforts toward quality education. Capacity building is not a new idea, but the department wants to invigorate and intensify it based on the needs of each school, especially the teachers. Before, we had the Training Needs Assessment (TNA), and later, we had the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS), and now we have our revised Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). All these were devised and made to strengthen and develop our teachers.

3.3. *Educational Insights Drawn From the Study*—

Fig. 4. The Emerging Themes on the Coping Mechanisms of Grade Three Teachers in Enhancing Parental Collaboration in Rural Areas

The parent-teacher relationship is a two-way path in which all parties should be involved to help the student progress and finish school.

This allows us to realize some insights that could help people, especially teachers, deal with parental involvement.

3.3.1. Attendance to trainings and seminars—Efforts to form and train teams of parents and educators offer the most direct route to using such partnerships to increase student achievement. Without the information and skills to communicate with each other, misperceptions and distrust can flourish between parents and school personnel. Most parents and school staff in most schools receive little training on how to work with one another. Special training for teachers and other school staff can play a key role in dispelling some of the misconceptions and stereotypes that become barriers to effective partnerships between parents and teachers. Schools report that lack of staff training in working with parents is a great or moderate barrier to parent involvement (U.S. Department of Education, 1997). Through workshops and a variety of outreach activities such as informative newsletters, handbooks, and home visits, parents and school staff across these programs are learning how to trust each other and work together to help children succeed in school. Their approaches include helping parents support learning at home, preparing parents to participate in school decision-making, and providing teachers, principals, and school staff with strategies for

reaching out to parents and working with them as partners. These approaches share an emphasis on training and information that is grounded in the needs and goals of families and school staff, and that focus on changing the negative attitudes that parents and school staff may hold towards each other. (Aman, 2010) According to Blake, some schools offer teachers, principals, and school staff information and strategies on how to reach out to parents and work with them as partners. This can be especially beneficial to school staff who typically receive little or no preservice training in these skills. In addition, changes in family structures and community life can require new or different family outreach strategies from what may have been effective in the past. Professional development activities may include sessions on making telephone calls, home visits, and other contact strategies, students' home culture and appreciating diversity, communication skills for parent-teacher conferences, and involving parents as leaders and decision-makers in the schools. Other schools have found that engaging parent coordinators or parent volunteers to train school staff not only builds parents' leadership skills but also offers teachers the opportunity to learn about families from parents' perspectives.

3.3.2. Effective communication—Communication and collaboration skills are essential tools for teacher-parent partnerships in all settings. Epstein (2005) defined communication as the ability to design effective school-to-home and home-to-school communication about school programs and student progress. Schools must take the initiative to create a good communication system between the school and

home (Epstein, 2011). Teachers' perceptions of parent involvement can be key elements in determining teachers' expectations of parents and how teachers communicate with parents. Communication between teachers and parents is a positive predictor of a student's enrollment at institutions (Ross, 2016). Thus, meaningful interaction between parents and teachers stems from teachers' approach when it comes to fos-

tering relationships that are perceived as positive by parents (Patel Stevens, 2010; Whitakers Hoover-Dempsey, 2013). Educating students requires teachers and parents to be integral parts of student growth and development in the learning process from the time students begin their high school careers until they matriculate to college. Teachers and parents must share and understand a student's learning experiences to communicate the value of learning to students (Hedges Gibbs, 2005). However, laying the groundwork for student academic success requires teacher and parent collaboration in nurturing the educational and social experiences of college preparatory students (O'Brien et al., 2013). Thus, the involvement and support of teacher-parent partnerships are essential parts of student academic preparation. Evidence suggests that teacher-parent partnerships require that educators have effective communication and collaboration skills. Avoiding misunderstanding in expectations requires teachers to understand and identify their collaborative roles and responsibilities with parents (Brueck et al.,

2012). Therefore, the problem is that educators at the school need the communication and collaboration competencies necessary for effective teacher-parent partnerships. Understanding the skills teachers need for effective teacher-parent partnerships will help to guide school leaders and systems in the development of policies, programs, and actions encouraging faculty involvement in family partnerships with parents (Epstein et al., 2019). To help to mitigate these discrepancies, teachers need to have the appropriate competencies for developing positive relationships with parents. When parents are involved in their child's education, teachers become more comfortable with communicating with parents which then leads to a positive relationship amongst the two (Radzi, Razak, Sukor, 2010). The goal of communication is to keep families informed about what is happening at school, keep them involved in programs, and keep them up to date on their child's academic progress (Epstein, 2011). Designing practices and activities with this goal in mind will help schools improve parental involvement levels.

3.3.3. Strengthen the collaboration of Teachers—Effective teacher-parent partnerships play an important role in student's academic preparation and success (Brueck et al., 2012). Parents' level of engagement is often a direct correlation to the school's effort to secure and build a trusting relationship. The primary influences on parental involvement and engagement are specific school programs staff practices and attitudes toward parents (Eccles Howard, 1993; Epstein, 1991). Teachers play a direct role when they monitor parents as they participate and volunteer in the classroom. They indirectly motivate parents to participate in school activities and home learning activities with their children (Barnyak McNelly, 2009). Teachers can be instrumental when it comes to parental involvement. According to Patterson, Webb,

and Krudwig (2009), if teachers do not take it upon themselves to collaborate and encourage parents to become involved, then parents may remain disengaged in their child's education. Therefore, collaboration between parents and teachers is necessary (Epstein, 2011; Hill Tyson, 2009; Jeynes, 2010). When collaboration occurs between parents and teachers, parents have more direct access to their child's education and can stay informed about significant developments. According to Griffin and Galasi (2010), students' chances of achieving academically increase when there is collaboration between parents and school staff in academics, attendance, and truancy. The parent-teacher partnership has a tremendous impact on children's education. According to Llamas and Tuazon (2016), parents become com-

fortable when the education system requires their involvement in school activities. Parents' strong collaboration with school authorities can lead to increased improvement in the school's physical and academic performance. Hence, school administrators must encourage parents to get involved and contribute to helping the school achieve its missions and goals (Sapungan Sapungan, 2014, p. 45). Seeing parents involved in their children's education is a good thing because it improves academic performance. Learners become more focused on their schoolwork (Kwatubana Makhalemele, 2015). This motivates learners not to give up easily when they do not understand a particular topic and will not bunk classes because they know their parents are always monitoring their school attendance (Lemmer, 2007, p. 320). Learners whose parents are involved are active and ready to learn; they learn to be punctual from a young age, and they learn to be persistent as the parents would be continuously enquiring about their progress, and they would not want to disappoint them. Taking responsibility becomes a part of the nature of such children as they plan ahead and are able to do their work according to their schedule, which is the quality of being organized (Sapungan Sapungan, 2014). Through this, parents should be able to make sure that their children succeed in school (Hornby Lafaele, 2011). These collaborations reflect Bronfenbrenner's bioecological systems theory of human development (BST), which emphasizes how individual and collaborative interactions in a system shape and influence a student's growth and development over time (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Demonstrated

through his theory on the ecology of human development, Bronfenbrenner (1979) explained the importance of a child's interaction with teachers and parents and how teacher-parent involvement impacts individual development from childhood to adulthood. In his exploration of the ecology of human development, Bronfenbrenner emphasized that collaborative relationships between school and family systems are instrumental in a student's growth and development (Froiland Davison, 2014). Ensure that each student gets the opportunity to contribute their best. Curating assignments or group activities for the students that improve their creative and soft skills. Giving students proper feedback to improve and guiding them in the right direction. Teacher collaboration days that are dedicated to various groups of teachers working (together or independently as needed) are important. This type of longer, more involved planning allows teachers to build deeper relationships, work without interruptions, and build a foundation for the upcoming school days. Ideally, there would be eight planning days a year. A possible schedule would be two days at the start of each quarter—even better if it's before school begins for students in the quarter. Not all schools or districts have the luxury of creating their schedules in this way, but if it's possible, it's worth making the time for this.

Figure 5 shows the educational management insights gained from the experiences of the informants and the emergence of the three themes: attendance to training and seminars, effective communication, and strengthened collaboration.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study summary. The findings are summarized, and the implications and future directions are drawn. The purpose of my study was to solicit the experiences of grade three teachers from Mati South District, Division of Mati City, to enhance parental collaboration in rural areas. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Gained from the Experiences of the Informants

with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, participants were encouraged to present their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. Findings—The findings of the study on the experiences of grade three teachers with enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas revealed that it was indeed collaborating with the community, challenging, trust and respect, and dedication and optimism. Regarding the coping mechanisms of grade three teachers with enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas, it was revealed that they cope by boosting collaboration, keeping the line of communication open, and capacitating teachers. As to the educational management insights gained from the participants, the grade three teachers proposed attendance at training and seminars, effective communication, and strengthened collaboration as essential insights in their experiences in enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. Based on the experiences of grade three teachers with enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas, the interview revealed the following themes: First, collaborating with the community. The teachers experienced collaboration with the community to help build trust between the school and the community, and it has encouraged more parents to get involved in their children's education. Second, challenging communication in the relationship that exists between parents and teachers can be described as both rewarding and challenging. Third, trust and respect, trust and respect between parents and teachers are critical elements in successful school-family cooperation. Fourth, dedication and optimism; in a school setting, where a teacher deals with varied kinds of people, dedication and optimism are much-needed traits. On the coping mechanisms of grade three teachers with enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas, one of the themes that was shown was boosting collaboration. The teachers cope with the challenges of enhancing parental collaboration by creating a culture of shared leadership and responsibility in order to enhance the involvement of parents. The second theme identified was keeping the line of communication open so teachers can share information about a student's good work and achievements. The third theme identified was capacitating teachers to encourage school-family partnerships through shared responsibilities, shared decision-making, and parity for all participants. On the educational management insights gained from grade three teachers with enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas, the first theme identified was attendance to training and seminars, as efforts to form and train teams of parents and educators offer the most direct route to the ultimate goal of using such partnerships to increase student achievement. The second theme identified was effective communication. Communication and collaboration skills are essential tools for teacher-parent partnerships in all settings. Avoiding misunderstanding in expectations requires teachers to understand and identify their collaborative roles and responsibilities with parents. The third theme was strengthening collaboration, as parents' level of engagement is often a direct correlation to the school's effort to secure and build a trusting relationship. Additionally, Effective teacher-parent partnerships play an important role in students' academic preparation and success.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the findings of the study, it was important that some important moves be taken into consideration and made available for primary school teachers, considering the bulk of their work on their assigned function as teachers enhancing parental collaboration in rural areas. This study may provide an avenue to enlighten the school heads to continue supporting their teachers in their endeavors to enhance parental collaborations in rural areas. It can provide valuable insights for school heads as they work to promote effective parental collaborations that support student success. Using evidence-based approaches and fostering collaboration and trust, school heads can create a supportive environment that benefits teachers, families, and students. The study can assist the grade three teachers in identifying effective strategies, highlighting challenges, and providing targeted professional development, which would be very beneficial for their strategies in enhancing the collaborative relationship between the teachers and the parents. The learners, along with their parents, should look into the possible contributions they could work on to further make their experience with parental collaborations better for them as learners, parents, and teachers. Similar studies may be conducted in other regions or divisions for future researchers. The researchers may consider other aspects of the experiences of the grade three teachers in enhancing parental collaborations in rural areas.

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